

Adsorption of Phenol from Aqueous Solution by Carbons as Influenced by Surface Oxygen Complexes

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Adsorption of phenol by sugar charcoal and carbon blacks from dilute aqueous solutions with concentrations upto ~20 millimoles/l is influenced considerably by the presence of chemisorbed oxygen. The presence of the combined oxygen as CO₂-complex imparts to the surface preference for water and thus affects adversely the adsorbability of phenol. The presence of the oxygen as CO-complex, on the other hand, improves the adsorbability of phenol, due, probably, to the interaction of quinonic oxygen of this complex with π electrons of the benzene ring, as well as the OH group of phenol. Thus the view of previous workers that the combined oxygen as a whole has an adverse effect on the adsorbability of phenol from aqueous solutions is not substantiated. The adsorption by oxygen-free carbons is influenced largely by porosity and surface area of the carbons.

ADSORPTION of phenol and other polar organic molecules from aqueous solution, under the influence of combined oxygen, has been examined by some workers in recent years. Graham¹, for example, has shown that the oxygen surface complexes tend to reduce the capacity for the adsorption of metanil yellow but not that for methylene blue from aqueous solution, although both the adsorbate molecules are of about the same size. Clauss et al² reported that adsorption of phenol from aqueous solution is not affected by surface oxides at all. Coughlin, Ezra and Tan³, on the other hand, have reported that adsorption not only of phenol but also of other organic compounds with polar groups, such as nitrobenzene and sodium benzene sulphonate, is reduced substantially in the presence of combined oxygen. Evidently, more work is needed to decide the issue. It would also be of interest to examine the role of individual surface oxygen complexes which come off as carbon dioxide (CO₂-complex) and as carbon monoxide (CO-complex), respectively. Adsorption of phenol by carbons is also of interest from the standpoint of water treatment and hence surface area and porosity of carbons are other features requiring attention.

Experimental

Three carbon blacks : Mogul (a colour black), Spheron-6 (a channel black) and Graphon (a highly graphitised carbon black), all supplied by Cabot Corporation, through the courtesy of Dr. Rivin, and a sample of charcoal, prepared by the carbonisation of recrystallised cane sugar⁴ and washed free of tarry matter with benzene, were used before as well as after outgassing⁵ at 600 and 1000°C. The amount of combined oxygen and the form of its disposition was obtained by evacuating 1g. (oven-dried at 120°) in a resistance tube furnace, the temperature of which was raised gradually to 1200° and analysing the gas (CO₂, CO and H₂O) evolved in the manner described before⁵. Surface acidity was estimated by titrating against aqueous barium hydroxide⁶ and surface area (nitrogen) by the usual B. E. T. method. The values for the various samples are presented in Table 1. It is seen that outgassing at 600° results in elimination of most of the acidic CO₂-complex and also of a small fraction of CO-complex while that at 1000° results in almost complete elimination of CO-complex as well. Surface acidity (barium hydroxide value) is seen to be quite close to the

TABLE 1—SURFACE AREAS, OXYGEN CONTENTS AND OXYGEN COMPLEXES OF THE VARIOUS SAMPLES

Description of the sample	Nitrogen Surface area (m ² /g.)	Oxygen content (g/100g.)	CO ₂ evolved (Total CO ₂ -complex) (mmole/100g.)	Ba(OH) ₂ value (Acidic CO ₂ -complex) (mmole/100g.)	Non-acidic CO ₂ -complex (mmole/100g.)	CO-complex (mole/100g.)
1.	2.	3.	4.	5.	6.	7.
<i>Sugar charcoal</i>						
Original	412	29.84	355	352	nil	531.3
600°-outgassed	514	9.48	50.5	49.2	nil	491.2
1000°-outgassed	502	nil	nil	nil	nil	nil
<i>Mogul</i>						
Original	308	7.83	69.0	68.5	nil	261.3
600°-outgassed	321	4.07	11.8	10.9	nil	230.7
1000°-outgassed	326	nil	nil	nil	nil	nil
<i>Spheron-6</i>						
Original	120	3.08	15.5	15.2	nil	132.5
600°-outgassed	128	1.82	2.5	2.4	nil	108.8
1000°-outgassed	118	nil	nil	nil	nil	nil
<i>Graphon</i>	76	nil	nil	nil	nil	nil

amount of CO_2 -complex. Surface area of sugar charcoal undergoes a significant change but that of a carbon black only a relatively minor change on outgassing at elevated temperatures.

Adsorption isotherms were determined at 35° ($\pm 0.1^\circ$). Carbon (0.5 g., oven-dried at 120°) was mixed with a known weight (~ 5 g.) of phenol solution of a given concentration and the suspension was allowed to stand in the thermostat with occasional shaking for about 24 hrs. The change in concentration, as a measure of adsorption, was determined interferometrically. The instrument used was a T. R. laboratory model supplied by Stankoimport, Moscow. The experiments were conducted in the low concentration range upto 20 m. moles/l. as adsorption in this range is likely to be more sensitive to the effect of chemisorbed oxygen and also more useful from the point of view of water treatment.

Results and Discussion

The isotherms on the various carbons in the original state, before giving them any evacuation treatment, are shown in Fig. 1. The values have been plotted in terms of amounts adsorbed (μ moles) per m^2 of surface, in order to eliminate the effect of different surface areas of the various carbons. It is seen that the extent of adsorption per m^2 of surface is maximum in the case of Graphon which is free of oxygen and minimum in the case of sugar charcoal which contains maximum amount of oxygen. In fact, the extent of adsorption decreases as we move from Graphon to Spheron-6, Mogul and sugar charcoal, i. e., in the order of samples containing increasing amounts of oxygen. Thus the role of chemisorbed oxygen in adversely affecting the magnitude of adsorption is quite evident.

Taking molecular area of phenol as 52.2 \AA^2 (assuming flat orientation³), it can be shown by simple calculations that adsorption of 3μ moles would be needed to give complete monolayer coverage to the surface. It is seen from the isotherms that the surface coverage in the present experiments, even at the maximum equilibrium concentration, comes upto only $\sim 40, 25, 20$ and 8 per cent in the case of Graphon, Spheron-6, Mogul and Sugar charcoal respectively. It may be noted that Coughlin et al had observed surface coverage of 5-40 per cent by phenol in the case of various activated carbons examined by them in the low concentration range. Morris and Weber⁷ observed more than one plateau in the isotherms for such systems before the completion of a monolayer.

In order to study the effect of combined oxygen more directly, and, in particular, that of the two complexes separately, the isotherms were also determined after outgassing each carbon at 600° and 1000° . The results are plotted in Fig. 2: (a), (b) and (c), for Spheron-6, Mogul and sugar charcoal, respectively. It is interesting to note that when the acidic CO_2 -complex is eliminated substantially on outgassing at 600° and CO -complex becomes the predominant surface complex, adsorption of phenol rises considerably in the case of each carbon and even surpasses the corresponding value for the oxygen-free sample at each concentration. This shows that the adverse effect of combined oxygen is confined only to the presence of the acidic CO_2 -complex and not to the whole of the combined oxygen, as has been reported by previous workers (*loc. cit.*). It is highly significant to note that when the combined oxygen is present as CO -complex, the interaction of phenol with the surface, far from diminishing, is enhanced to an appreciable extent. This positive effect of a part of the

Fig. 1. Adsorption Isotherms of Phenol (35°) on Graphon, Sugar Charcoal, Mogul and Spheron-6

Fig. 2. Adsorption Isotherms of Phenol (35°) on Spheron-6, Mogul and Sugar Charcoal before and after outgassing at 600 and 1000°.

combined oxygen in enhancing the sorption of phenol, from aqueous solution is being reported, probably, for the first time. The effect is a little more pronounced in the case of Spheron-6 which had, relatively, a larger fraction of the combined oxygen as CO-complex.

In order to explain the adverse effect of the combined oxygen on the sorption of phenol, Coughlin et al postulated that the combined oxygen is located at the edges of the layer planes and hence they localise the π electron system of the basal planes. This leads to weakening of the interaction between the phenol π electron system and the π band of the graphitic planes of the carbon. In view of the fact that a part of the combined oxygen actually enhances the sorption of phenol, the above explanation does not appear to hold good.

It has been shown in some recent publications from these laboratories⁸⁻¹⁰ that while the combined oxygen present as CO₂-complex imparts hydrophilicity and polarity to the surface that present as CO-complex, which arises from the presence of quinonic groups, renders the surface benzophilic in character due, probably, to the interaction of π electrons of benzene with partial positive charge on quinonic oxygen¹¹. It appears highly likely, therefore, that when CO₂-complex is predominant, the surface prefers the strongly polar molecules of water (i. e., the solvent) to molecules of phenol. This has an adverse effect on the adsorbability of phenol by the carbon. However, with the elimination of most of this complex and with the emergence of

CO-as the predominant surface complex, the preference of the surface for phenol rises appreciably on account of the interaction of π electrons of benzene ring with the quinonic oxygen, as mentioned above. There may be some interaction between the OH group of phenol and the quinonic oxygen on the surface as well which will also tend to raise the adsorbability of phenol by the carbon. These differences in interactions of the two kinds of surface oxygen complexes appear to offer a fairly satisfactory explanation for the results presented in this paper.

The isotherms on oxygen-free carbons (1000°-outgassed samples) including Graphon are plotted separately in Fig. 3. It is seen that the sorption on sugar charcoal per m.² of surface is far less than that on any of the carbon blacks. This appears to be due to high degree of porosity of the adsorbent as a result of which the internal surface, which constitutes a major fraction of the total in this case, remains inaccessible to phenol molecules having area of 52.2 Å². The isotherms on the rest of the samples, however, are fairly close to one another. This shows that adsorption of phenol by carbon blacks, which are free of oxygen and do not differ much in their porosity, is largely a function of surface area.

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Fig. 3. Adsorption Isotherms of Phenol (35°) on various carbons free of oxygen.

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